

Applying John Dewey's Experiential Learning Model to Organize Life Skills Education Activities for Elementary School Students

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Suggested Citation

Linh, D.T.M. (2024). Applying John Dewey's Experiential Learning Model to Organize Life Skills Education Activities for Elementary School Students. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(4), 760-769. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(4\).65](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(4).65)

Abstract:

Life skills education for primary school students is one of the important educational tasks to achieve the goal of educational innovation as well as meet the needs of national development in the context of integration. There are many solutions to implement life skills education activities for elementary school students, in which applying experience to the organization of educational activities is one of the solutions that is of great interest. The theory of experience shows the important role of experience in organizing life skills education for elementary school students. Based on Dewey's experiential learning model consisting of 4 steps representing the

process of forming students' knowledge and skills, the article proposes a process for organizing life skills education for elementary students based on experience. This process includes 8 steps that demonstrate the process of organizing educational activities of teachers to help students participate in the learning process and promote their strengths, create students' interest participating in educational activities and contribute to the learning process part of improving the effectiveness of life skills education for elementary school students.

Keywords: *Life skills education, experiential learning model, elementary school students.*

Introduction

Life skills education for elementary school students aims to equip students with many skills such as: Self-protection and development skills; Communication skills with friends; Family behavioral skills; Study and communication skills in school; Communication and social behavioral skills; Survival skills... (Huynh Van Son, 2017). Besides the following media, the application of experiential learning theory in life skills education is increasingly interested by many educators because applying experiential learning theory in life skills education has can form positive habits for students in daily life, hard work; Carry out student responsibilities at home, school and locality; know how to self-evaluate

and self-adjust; Forming subsequent communication behaviors and cultural applications; have a sense of group rationality and form problem-solving capacity (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018).

For a long time, many researchers have considered research and applied experience in education with the goal of increasing student learning outcomes. Since 1925, John Dewey has researched theories related to the process of forming students' knowledge through experience (Dewey, 1925). Afterwards, many other scientists also researched this issue, Jean Piaget pointed out that the nature and origin of human knowledge formation is the product of the interaction between the subject and the

environment (Piaget, 1972). Edgar Dale argued that learners retain more information by what they “do” as opposed to what they “hear,” “read,” or “observe” (Dale, 1969). John Dewey believed that reflection is a logical process of beginning to experience a problem. He argued that educational activity does not occur until after observation and judgment have occurred and that each subsequent experience is based on past experiences (Dewey, 1990). In 1984, David Kolb, head of the research establishment of Dewey, Lewin, Piaget, Vygotsky and other researchers on experience and experiential learning, said: “Learning is the process in which that formulaic architecture is created through experiential transformation” (Kolb, 1984; Kolb & Sharma, 2014). Arthur Chickering believes that the experiential learning process results when there is a change in the learner's emotions and knowledge through situations occurring in the main learner's life; Through experience, learners will change their own behavior, knowledge, and attitudes (Chickering, 1977). David Boud, Ruth Cohen, and David Walker have identified the characteristics and roles of experiential educational work that underpin and stimulate learning (Boud et al., 1993). Jack Mezirow argues that experience is based on the architecture of previous experiences. Learning occurs when there is a transformation of beliefs, attitudes and emotional responses including that changed knowledge, skills and the acquisition of new perspectives (Mezirow, J., 2000). Cameron Atkinson also believes that experiential learning is learning by doing, the learner is an active participant in the educational process, not a passive witness (Atkinson, 2017).

Organizing educational activities through experiences helps students gain many necessary life experiences. Therefore, teachers apply a number of experiential learning models to lesson design because experience helps students form and apply practical knowledge and skills naturally without having to memorize them. In addition, students have the opportunity to promote self-study and creativity. However, how to effectively use the experiential learning model in lesson design is one of the issues of concern. This article studies John Dewey's experiential

learning theory and model, suggesting a process for applying the experiential learning model to designing life skills education lessons for elementary school students.

Research Content and Results

Life Skills Education for Elementary School Students

Life skills education for elementary school students can be done through subjects, experiential activities in school and life skills practice.

- Life skills education for elementary school students is carried out through subjects such as: Ethics, Nature and Society; Maths. To form knowledge and practice life skills for students through subjects, teachers need to know how to apply many teaching methods to promote students' positivity, initiative and creativity such as: practicing actions in communication, practice actions in game activities through methods and problem solving, methods of organizing group learning activities, conversation methods, question and answer methods, debate.
- Life skills education through experiential activities in school such as labor, group activities and social activities have greatly contributed to forming students' personalities, helping them learn and practice on their own practice and perfect yourself.
- Life skills education through life skills practice: In elementary school, life skills education is carried out 1 period/week in an effort to help students form specific skills such as skills to protect and develop themselves, skills to communicate with friends, behavior skills in the family, learning and communication skills in school, survival skills.

John Dewey's Experiential Learning Model

During the learning process of listening to lectures, students will passively receive knowledge (McAuliffe, 2011). Dewey believes that students learn more effectively and have more experiences when they are strongly and actively involved in the learning process (Dewey

J., *The psychology of effort*, 1897) (Dewey J., 1933). He proposed a model of how learning transforms the impulses, feelings and desires of

concrete experience into higher-order, purposeful action (Dewey J., 1938).

Figure 1. Dewey's Model of Reactive Thought and Action

The thinking and action model specifically describes the student's transformation into action from thinking to experiencing action through 5 steps as follows:

- Stirring up creates conflict between habits and situations

The starting point of experience is not how the experience is understood or the individual's reaction to action but the recognition of the internal conflict of the person or the conflict between the person and the environment.

Some problems in situations make it impossible to resolve thoroughly with normal actions, creating conflicts that require people to reflect and find other, more appropriate solutions. This leads to direct inhibition of action, which is a necessary prerequisite for retrospective thinking. Thinking clearly begins by studying the conditions in which the problem occurs, the resources for solving the problem the advantages and disadvantages of action.

- Brainstorming, reflection and definitional issues

The rethinking process begins with an attempt to determine what is wrong with the situation. Identify the problem and its cause. The formulation of the problem is presupposed when studying the conditions of the situation and the evolution of the problem situation itself. Dewey emphasized the importance of identifying problems in thinking. Without identifying the problem, action will be groped in the dark.

- Research the conditions of the situation and information of the hypotheses

Analyze and expect the conditions that occur when we choose a way to solve a problem includes both the physical and social conditions, means and resources by which the problem is expected to be resolved.

- Reasoning to find ways to solve problems

Reasoning aims to determine the meaning of ideas and ways to solve different problems. Reasoning can clearly visualize each hypothetical solution to a problem. The ability to choose hypotheses for action can be evaluated and tested against the knowledge and resources available to an individual or a community. These arguments are very important because if we find that the way to solve the problem is not effective, we can go back to solving the problem from the beginning.

- Action to test the hypothesis

The act of hypothetically solving a problem is realized in practice. Dewey said that the mere testing of a hypothesis allows us to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of the hypothesis. The situation must be built according to the requirements of the hypothesis,

to see whether the system derived from the hypothesis will become a reality in reality.

The thinking and action model shows the process from starting to think about how to solve the problem until forming a definition for solving the problem or how to act to solve the problem. Dewey believes that reflection is a logical process of beginning to experience a problem. He emphasizes conscious reflection as an important part of experiential learning (Jordan et al.(2008)). He also believes that educational activity does not occur until observation and judgment have occurred. In other words, education is characterized by observations from an experience, reflecting on that experience and then forming concepts based on those reflections and pre-existing knowledge. Dewey also pointed out that each subsequent experience builds on past experiences, thus indicating that the experiential learning process proceeds as follows (Dewey J., 1990) (Kolb D., 1984):

Figure 2. John Dewey's Concept of Experiential Learning According to Kolb

The procedure shows that in the first stage students are presented with an ambiguous problem, which still does not have a precise solution (Dewey, 1925; McAuliffe, 2011). From there, students think about some ways to solve the problem and realize that their previous experiences are not enough to solve the problem. Students participate in experiences, observe experiences, and find knowledge to solve problems in new ways. Perform problem solving in similar situations to evaluate newly acquired knowledge. From there, students gain

experience in solving new problems and so on in a spiral. The following experiences are based on previous experiences. Each experience starts with a previous experience, then reflects on the experience and situation, then forms concepts and existing knowledge from which to draw the next experience.

Step 7: Teachers organize educational activities so that students can demonstrate the knowledge they have learned after participating in the experience, reflect and draw out the knowledge and skills needed to solve the situations they have experienced.

Step 8: Teachers organize educational activities to evaluate learners' responses and compare them with the learners' initial experiences and form new experiences.

The experience of organizing activities is organized in a spiral, each spiral cycle consists of 8 steps and the learner's experience gradually increases in a spiral until gathering enough experience to perform a task, in education. Educating life skills for students, the main task is a life skill, each step has a certain meaning in the work to help learners develop their own knowledge but under the leadership and organization of the members. Each educational step will apply relevant theories in designing educational activities such as experiencing methods of organizing activities, active teaching methods, educational methods, stating goals according to verbs indicating the level of achievement of Bloom's cognitive scale to easily evaluate students according to each skill.

Design a Life Skills Education Plan for Elementary School Students According to John Dewey's Experiential Learning Model

Principles of organizing educational activities through experience

Atkinson gave some principles when organizing educational activities through experiential activities as follows (Atkinson, 2017):

- Define clearly goals to be able to evaluate the level of assessment according to Bloom's cognitive scale.
- Allow enough time for students to think about the experience.
- Ask clear questions, consistent with the goal of organizing experiential activities appropriate to each topic.
- Plan appropriate activities will help students reflect on their experiences while participating in educational activities.
- Listen carefully to student feedback to make adjustments and orientations for students to change their experiences most appropriately.
- Support each student who has difficulty participating in experiential activities.

Applying John Dewey's experiential learning model to design life skills education activities for elementary school students

Applying the process of organizing life skills education for elementary school students and experiential information into designing life skills education plans for elementary school students. Within the scope of the article, the author designs sample educational activities for 2nd grade students, group work skills lesson.

The outcome to educate teamwork skills (Huynh Van Son, 2017):

- State the requirements for group work.
- Explain requirements for group work.
- Fulfill requirements when working in groups.

Table 1. Plan to Educate Teamwork Skills for 2nd Grade Students Through Experience

<i>Step</i>	<i>Teacher's activities</i>	<i>Student's activities</i>
1. Exploit experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teachers exploit students' experiences through questions: - Do you like working in groups or individually? - In your opinion, how can each member of the group help the group complete the task well? <p>According to you, when working in groups, if your opinion is different from the opinions of your group members, what should you do?</p>	<p>Students listen and answer questions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Things to do when working in groups are reaching consensus, assigning tasks, ... + Respect each other's opinions, don't look down on you, ... + Listen to your opinions, express your thoughts.

2. Identify goals	<p>The teacher provides the lesson objective: "Today's lesson helps you fulfill the requirements when working in groups. To fulfill the requirements of group work, we must state and explain the requirements of group work and apply these requirements when working in group to perform a task .</p>	Listen and remember
3. Provide experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Divide the class into several groups, each group has 4-6 students. The teacher organized the students to do group work with the task of completing a card to give to the teacher on Vietnamese Teachers' Day November 20. - The teacher assigns the task: "To get a beautiful card, what tasks do you have to do and how do you work in groups?" - The teacher provides students with several types of cards with materials, shapes, decorations and card content (Sample cards are in the Appendix). - The teacher summarizes the things to do and requirements when working in groups to complete the card. To complete the card you must: Determine the tasks to complete the card such as choosing materials, colors, sizes, decorations, local layout, techniques required to cut such as cutting, cutting, cutting, etc. Organize for students to present the discussed products using the gallery technique. The groups take turns posting the paintings discussed by the group on the walls around the classroom. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Groups discuss and propose requirements for group work to make cards for teachers. - Determine the tasks to complete the card such as choosing materials, colors, sizes, card shapes, decorations, decorative layout, techniques needed to make cards such as cutting, tearing, draw, ... <p>Students assign members to perform tasks, draw, collage, write wishes,...</p>
4 Describe the Experience	<p>The groups sent representatives to report on two tasks as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Tell us about the group work process, such as the group assigning tasks to group members, how effective the group work was, and what advantages or difficulties appeared during the group work process? + The group proposes requirements for group work, analyzes which actions are correct and which actions are incorrect when working in groups, and explains why group work is necessary. 	<p>Students send representatives to report the results of the discussion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Describe in detail the group work process + Suggest things to avoid when doing group work. + Suggest things to do when working in groups.
5. Organization of experiences processing	<p><i>Teachers use the form of reflection on experiences through videos. The teacher organizes for students to watch video number 1 describing requirements for group work.</i></p> <p>The video simulates a situation where two groups perform the same task.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group 1: During group work, members of group 1 fully fulfilled the requirements when working in groups, so the results of completing the task were very good. - Group 2: During group work, the students did not meet the requirements of group work, such as not assigning tasks but working individually, not respecting each other's opinions, so they could not complete the task like group 1. <p>The teacher divides the class into groups, each group has 4-6 students.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher suggests for students to reflect: "You observe the video and tell me, to complete the work well, what requirements do we need to pay attention to when working in groups and why do we need to do them?" - The teacher introduces the next video: "To explain why group work is needed, let's watch the next 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students observe video number 1 - Students realize that the two groups have different results when working together. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students assign tasks to group members (taking notes, reporting) - Students are assigned to record all group members' observations of the actions of the characters in video number 1. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students observe video 2 - Students observe the group work results of the groups in the video.

	<p>video."</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teacher organizes for students to watch Video No. 2 describes the Power of teamwork. The video depicts characters who seem to be weaker, but thanks to the rhythm of teamwork, they can and defeat stronger people to protect their own safety. The teacher assigns the task: "After observing the 2 videos, in your opinion, when working in groups, compare with the experiences you have had when working in groups, what requirements do you need to ensure and why do we need group work?" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students realize what it would be like to complete the task if they did not work in groups. - Students are assigned to record all group members' observations of the actions of the characters in video number 2. Students reflect on the actions of the characters in the two videos with their own previous experiences and draw out the content of the report.
6. Rethink	<p>The teacher asks the question:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can you tell me that after reading the results of many groups' discussions about the requirements for group work, what have you learned about the requirements for group work? - According to you, during group work, there are some people who have different opinions from you. How should you handle this problem? - According to you during group work, how can everyone in the group participate in performing the task? - The teacher summarizes the requirements for group work: Elect a group leader, determine your abilities, assign tasks, while doing so you must listen and respect your opinions. <p>Teachers organize students to participate in games to reinforce the requirements for group work.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The teacher divides the class into teams, each team has 6-10 students. <p>The teacher explains how to play: Each person in the group chooses group work requirements and arranges them in the order posted on the board. Game rules: Each person only chooses one request, then goes to the next person. Continue like this until all the given cards are gone. The group that completes the task first wins.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students think and list requirements when working in groups. - Students mentioned how to handle different opinions: to listen, analyze, and present opinions to get the best opinions. - Students assign tasks to members, pay attention to the opinions they have just drawn after group work, elect a group leader, determine the members' abilities, and assign tasks appropriate to their abilities, while performing, must listen and respect the opinions of group members. - Students participate in the game, assign group members to participate in order - Students analyze and understand the meaning of the cards, select cards with requirements for group work and the order of tasks to be done in group work. <p>Group members gradually paste cards with requirements for group work on the board in order</p>
7. Feedback	<p>Teachers organize a contest called "Grateful to teachers"</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Divide the class into groups, each group has 6-10 students. - The teacher assigned the task "The group's task is to complete a card to give to teachers on the occasion of Vietnamese Teachers' Day November 20 within 20 minutes." - The teacher sets the evaluation criteria for the cards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + About form: Perfect card, beautifully arranged, balanced, beautifully decorated, unique, creative, material,... + About content: Meaningful content expressing gratitude to teachers, good wishes, ... <p>The teacher chooses 2 groups to present how the group works</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Group 1: The group that achieves the best results presents how the group works to achieve good results. + Group 2: The group with the lowest results, presenting the difficulties the group encountered when working in groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students fulfill the requirements when working in groups to complete the task. - Groups elect group leaders - Nhóm trưởng phân công nhiệm vụ cho từng thành viên, cắt, vẽ, tô màu, ... - Groups fulfill requirements during group work, respect each other, listen and take responsibility for completing assigned tasks. - Students participate in voting for products of other groups. - Students and teacher choose 1 group with the most beautiful card and 1 not-so-beautiful or unfinished card. <p>The two groups sent representatives to share the group's advantages and disadvantages in the process of implementing the product so that others could learn from their experience.</p>

	The teacher summarizes, praises the group for good results and reiterates the requirements for group work.	
8. Valuation	Through playing games, and working in groups according to group work requirements. Teachers evaluate the level of completion of lesson objectives on the life skills assessment sheet for students.	Students listen and remember

At the end of step 8, students have fulfilled the requirements when working in groups. Just like that for the next goals in the goal of educating life skills for elementary school students. Don't stop at this topic, but ending this topic is the starting experience for the next experience.

Conclusion

Applying John Dewey's experiential teaching model to organizing life skills education for elementary school students helps students transform from thinking into action - an important issue in the goal of skills education living for elementary school students. With those positive contributions, up to now, his theory of experience is still respected by the world and continues to be researched and applied in many fields of education. The design and organization of experiential activities need to be flexible, creative, and suitable for each student, learning content, and school and local conditions. Applying the experiential learning model to organizing experiential activities can be flexible but still needs to ensure complete steps; at the same time, teachers will participate as instructors and promote the learning process; students can experience and summarize new experiences for themselves.

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